

Table 1: MCDA for evaluating molecules to treat patients with DLBCL

MCDA Step & Description	Applications, Lessons Learnt & Recommendations																																																											
<p>1. Defining the decision problem</p> <p>Agree on a shared definition of the problem, select molecules to be evaluated, and determine the required outputs and stakeholders involved.</p>	<p>Support the choice of which molecules in the pipelines to progress from PII to PIII and improve the probability of making the right choice.</p> <p>Application in DLBCL, between 2 hypothetical molecules for illustration.</p> <p>The DDT included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Committee members familiar with the disease (oncologists with expertise in treating patients with DLBCL) • Biostatisticians • Committee members familiar with the trial designs for the molecules of interest and the profile of competitor products; and regulators’ payers’ concerns. • Representatives of internal stakeholders on the DDT 																																																											
<p>2. Selecting and structuring criteria</p> <p>Identify criteria relevant for evaluating the molecules, ensuring they meet the properties for an additive aggregation (see Marsh et al., 2016 for more details on properties).</p>	<p><i>Benefit endpoints:</i> Disease Progression, Response (not sustained), Sustained-Response</p> <p><i>Risk endpoints:</i> Fatal AEs, SAEs (excluding septic shock), AEs leading to withdrawal (excluding septic shock or IRR), Grade 3-4 AEs (excluding septic shock or IRR), Septic shock, IRR</p> <p>Challenges encountered:</p> <p>Availability of data, selecting a manageable set of criteria, ensuring the requirements had desired properties (preference independence and non-overlap). This required restructuring specific criteria and evaluating whether it would be possible to estimate the performance of these newly defined criteria.</p>																																																											
<p>3. Measuring performance</p> <p>Gather performance data on the molecules for each criterion, including uncertainty</p>	<p>Incidence rates (95% CI) of outcomes at one year:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="808 1245 1568 1717"> <thead> <tr> <th colspan="2"></th> <th colspan="2">Outcomes at 1 year</th> <th>Drug A (n=703) (mean, LCI-UCI)</th> <th>Drug B (n=704) (mean, LCI-UCI)</th> </tr> <tr> <th></th> <th></th> <th>Min</th> <th>Max</th> <th></th> <th></th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td rowspan="3">EFFICACY</td> <td>Response sustained</td> <td>60%</td> <td>72%</td> <td>72.0% (68.56-75.19)</td> <td>67.5% (63.94-70.85)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Response not sustained</td> <td>2%</td> <td>8%</td> <td>6.0% (4.47-8.00)</td> <td>7.7% (5.95-9.91)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Progressed</td> <td>10%</td> <td>20%</td> <td>13.3% (10.99-16.01)</td> <td>11.5% (9.35-14.07)</td> </tr> <tr> <td rowspan="6">RISKS</td> <td>Fatal AE</td> <td>4%</td> <td>7%</td> <td>5.5% (4.04-7.44)</td> <td>4.0% (2.78-5.71)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>SAE</td> <td>30%</td> <td>36%</td> <td>33.0% (29.62-36.56)</td> <td>32.9% (29.52-36.46)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>AEs leading to withdrawal - other than septic shock or IRR</td> <td>1%</td> <td>10%</td> <td>6.0% (4.47-8.00)</td> <td>4.0% (2.78-5.71)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Grade 3-4 AEs – other than septic shock or IRR</td> <td>60%</td> <td>72%</td> <td>64.0% (60.38-67.46)</td> <td>62.0% (58.35-65.51)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Septic shock</td> <td>0%</td> <td>4%</td> <td>2.0% (1.20-3.32)</td> <td>2.1% (1.27-3.44)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>IRR</td> <td>3%</td> <td>12%</td> <td>5.1% (3.70-6.98)</td> <td>5.0% (3.62-6.87)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Colors reflect the difference in performances: green: better performance, orange: poorer performance, no color: similar performance.</p>			Outcomes at 1 year		Drug A (n=703) (mean, LCI-UCI)	Drug B (n=704) (mean, LCI-UCI)			Min	Max			EFFICACY	Response sustained	60%	72%	72.0% (68.56-75.19)	67.5% (63.94-70.85)	Response not sustained	2%	8%	6.0% (4.47-8.00)	7.7% (5.95-9.91)	Progressed	10%	20%	13.3% (10.99-16.01)	11.5% (9.35-14.07)	RISKS	Fatal AE	4%	7%	5.5% (4.04-7.44)	4.0% (2.78-5.71)	SAE	30%	36%	33.0% (29.62-36.56)	32.9% (29.52-36.46)	AEs leading to withdrawal - other than septic shock or IRR	1%	10%	6.0% (4.47-8.00)	4.0% (2.78-5.71)	Grade 3-4 AEs – other than septic shock or IRR	60%	72%	64.0% (60.38-67.46)	62.0% (58.35-65.51)	Septic shock	0%	4%	2.0% (1.20-3.32)	2.1% (1.27-3.44)	IRR	3%	12%	5.1% (3.70-6.98)	5.0% (3.62-6.87)
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<p>4. Scoring alternatives</p> <p>Elicitation of stakeholders' preferences within criteria and consistency checks</p>	<p>We used a two-step approach to elicit the scoring of outcomes within criteria and checked linearity (e.g., whether each additional fatality or each newly responding patient is valued equally). A single breakpoint was evaluated using the bisection method if it was not valued equally. For criteria with narrow ranges of performance, stakeholders assumed linearity. For those with more extensive ranges, we applied piecewise value functions.</p>
<p>5. Weighting criteria</p> <p>Elicitation of stakeholders' preferences/priorities between criteria and consistency checks</p>	<p>Weighting the performance of each asset by the key stakeholders allows a comparison of the overall value of assets on a single standard scale. We used the swing weighting method to elicit the weights/priorities among the criteria. Weights are a numerical representation of subjective values and thus can be challenging for stakeholders to provide. We presented Committee members with the marginal rates of substitution between criteria implied by the weights they provided. They were allowed to revisit their weight estimates until they generated a marginal rate of substitution they were satisfied with.</p> <p>Two committee members contributed weights. Preferences were heterogeneous. One of the oncologists put more weight on improving 'Response-Sustained' and reducing 'Grade 3-4 AEs'. The other oncologist put more weight on reducing 'Fatal AEs' and 'AEs leading to withdrawal.' Preferences for the other endpoints are relatively similar (Figure 1).</p> <p>Figure 1: Normalized weights for the two stakeholders (DM1=oncologist 1; DM2=Oncologist 2)</p>
<p>6. Calculating aggregate scores</p> <p>Using an additive function to aggregate the scores and weights and obtain an overall value of the molecules.</p>	<p>The assessment of the molecules was sensitive to the variation weights provided by the two committee members (Figure 2). The source of this difference was the weight attached to "Sustained-Response," "Fatal AEs," and "Grade 3-4 AEs".</p>

<p>MCDCA Step & Description</p>	<p>Applications, Lessons Learnt & Recommendations</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Figure 2: Overall value for the two stakeholders</p> </div>
<p>7. Dealing with uncertainty</p> <p>Exploring the impact of uncertainty around performance estimates to evaluate the benefit-risk balance of molecules.</p>	<p>Given the uncertainty in model inputs, the evaluation was run probabilistically to assess the likelihood that one therapy is preferred to another, given the uncertainty of the performance estimates.</p> <p>The output from the probabilistic running of the evaluation was a scatter plot on a benefit-risk plane (Figure 3). Both molecules had a positive B-R balance. Committee Member 1 viewed the B-R profile of both drugs more positively than Committee Member 2.</p> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Figure 3: Probabilistic Sensitivity Analysis: Benefit-Risk-Plane for Two Stakeholders</p> </div> <p>Committee member 2 is confident about their ranking of the drugs, with a 95% probability that they prefer Therapy B. Committee member one is less certain, with a 57% probability that they prefer Therapy A (Figure 4)</p>

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<p>8. Reporting and interpretation</p> <p>Interpretation of the MCDA outputs, sensitivity analyses, and evaluation of implications for decision-making</p>	<p>Results show that the benefit-risk is sensitive to individual committee member weights for outcomes, particularly the preference for “Response-Sustained” and “Grade 3-4 AEs”, and on reducing ‘Fatal AEs’ and ‘AEs leading to withdrawal. Identifying that committee member weights produce divergent decisions and which of their weights drive this divergence is an important starting point for committee deliberation to conclude. If committee members cannot align on weights, collecting patient or regulator preferences for endpoints may provide additional value to this analysis.</p>																		